

Leveraging the power of C-ITS with collaborative routing in urban areas

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Abstract

Road users increasingly use in-car navigation systems or smartphone navigation apps to reach their destination. However, the navigation providers are disconnected from the recommendations of road authorities and cannot predict sporadic traffic from special events, consequently they direct traffic onto low capacity streets that quickly get congested. These navigation shortcuts lead to anger from residents, while municipal authorities are unable to hinder the mass transit of vehicles through their streets. Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) restore the communication between road authorities and drivers. In the Hanover area, an interactive traffic management platform was developed and implemented, providing authorities the ability to control road usage based on the purpose of travel, the destination, the time and the vehicle category. The direct interaction with interconnected NUNAV navigation apps allows traffic management authorities to take back control. During special events, a market share of more than 10% was reached and the traffic flow significantly improved.

Keywords:

Collaborative Routing, Interactive Traffic Management, C-ITS

Introduction

Special events, for instance concerts and fairs attracting up to 26 000 cars and 1 000 buses, impose a unique strain on the road network. The proportions of visitors using public transport, touring coaches or individual transportation by car depends heavily on the type of event, its audience and the weather. The multitude of different demands of the road network are typically contrary and in conflict with each other. Visitors need to find a free parking space while touring coaches and visitors with disabilities need to reach designated parking spots and electric cars want a charging station all while the daily urban and commuting traffic puts the same load of traffic on the road network as usual. Local authorities and event organisers react to these challenges by setting up roadblocks to separate traffic flows and use manual parking space management and their staff to direct vehicles to free parking spots. If residents are affected by road closures, especially in the case of marathons and city runs, they need to be informed and are provided with practical support in the form of travel instructions.

Car drivers commonly try to circumvent congestions by using smartphone navigation apps. Shortcuts previously unknown to strangers have now become general knowledge in order to reach their final destination. Especially foreign drivers without local knowledge are more likely to follow the instructions of their navigation system than conventional or dynamic road signs. However, as navigation services are not aware of the additional travel demand due to special events, these low capacity shortcuts are

quickly jammed leading to dangerous situations [1]. With navigation services not able to follow the advice of local authorities for a variety of reasons, traffic becomes "unmanageable" [2].

Often, local authorities and event organisers react to these accrued road capacity challenges by setting up roadblocks, hence blocking out drivers not following main roads to the event location. Just to add another dimension, municipal authorities might block roads not known to federal road authorities and police officers not familiar with traffic management might set up roadblocks unknown to federal road authorities as well. Public entities also have a different perspective on parking management itself as private parking companies might define parking roles into categories such as visitors, exhibitors etc. All in all, traffic flow management and manual parking space management and their staff is not directed by one entity, but by their respective entities. In part, this is due to different local, federal and state policies, budget constraints or simply a lack in their digital progress. Traffic management authorities have in this case a rather reacting role. They can only act once traffic flow is affecting their designated area of authority like a motor way or a federal road.

Road closures on federal roads like the autobahn or federal streets are largely known to a cars navigation system through the commercial TIC system used by federal authorities in Germany and Europe. For inner-city road closures, especially in the case of marathons and city runs, a TIC-based system has difficulties to solely block left or right turns as for their compatibility with the ancient Traffic Message Channel (TMC) standard. In other cities, the system is absent and they don't provide machine readable information about road closures. All in all, the different digitalisation standards of one authority to another provides a challenge to all stakeholders and puts additional strain on traffic management and the respective authorities. A digital traffic management solution has to connect all stakeholders and collect and distribute traffic management information during all phases of the event. The road closures and road incidents then have to make their way into navigation apps in order to stay relevant with the ever-increasing smartphone community.

Requirements on Mobile Navigation Apps

While the proliferation of smartphone navigation app usage is part of the problem, it can also be part of the solution. With a smartphone available to almost every car owner, a mobile navigation app connected to the internet enables a large proportion of vehicles to connect to interactive traffic management. By providing a mobile navigation app to visitors, touring coach drivers and residents, they can be informed in real time about road closures and receive strategic traffic management information. The generated floating car data (FCD) is used by local authorities to monitor the traffic state, which is also taken into account for route calculation.

Connected: The routing has to follow instructions from local or federal authorities based on their respective authority. Currently in-car and mobile navigation systems incorporate information delivered via TIC and/or TMC. However, these channels are too slow and limited in scope and often don't play back the real state of a roads segment. In the case of special events, information on road closures need to be detailed all the way down to small roads, individual turns and distributed in real time to a navigation audience, based on their purpose of travel. Real-time event information services and real-time traffic

conditions information services have the potential to reduce the time spend in congestion by up to 15% respectively [3].

Collaborative: The impact of other vehicles on traffic needs to be taken into account. Typically, navigation systems base their estimation of travel time only on historic and current road usage. This approach falls short in the case of special events. When e.g. after a concert 25 000 drivers simultaneously start their routing, their impact needs to be taken into account during route calculation, to distribute their load on the road network. When all vehicles are routed to the same fastest road, it will get congested. But then it is too late, to diverge traffic onto alternative routes. Thus, the anticipated route has to be shared and coordinated with the other road users in real time.

Parking: When travelling to an event, visitors typically type the name of the venue in their navigation system and start searching for a parking space after they have reached their destination. This often leads to traffic jams and back jams to the connected motorways or access roads or visitors parking their cars in no-parking zones to reach the event in time. To avoid this additional cause of traffic, the navigation system should directly route vehicles to a free parking spot based on a user's purpose of travel and its role. When several parking spaces are available, the space reachable with lowest traffic impact should be chosen, over what is best for private parking companies.

Visitor role: When starting the navigation to an event, users should indicate whether they need reach a parking spot for visitors with disabilities or depending on the event a parking space for press or VIPs. In the case of sporting events, it might be necessary to separate followers of the competing teams. The software should also distinguish the vehicle type such that touring coaches might e.g. avoid bridges with weight restrictions.

Requirements on an Interactive Traffic Management Platform

To manage inner city traffic especially in the case of special events, administration on national and regional level, the police, event organisers and parking space managers must communicate and share information from their areas of authority. Traffic management instructions need to be exchanged in real time and define exact start and end time. Especially in urban areas, road closures need to be detailed down to the level of individual turns.

Events: During large scale events, special solutions are required. To divert traffic from streets, that are likely to get congested due to commuting traffic and event visitors not following the recommendations, virtual road closures need to be set up. Another option is, to define corridors for event traffic. Then, different types of vehicles could be directed on different corridors.

Parking space management: To be able direct visitors directly to a free parking space, the number available spots must be updated in real time.

Monitoring: The traffic state aggregated from FCD needs to be visualised such that traffic planers can base their discussions on the data.

Parking & Traffic Management Dashboard

The project "Parking management in combination with traffic management" started in 2017 as a cooperation between the Traffic Management Authority of Lower Saxony/Region of Hanover and Graphmasters, developer of the NUNAV family of navigation apps. A parking & traffic management dashboard was developed in close cooperation with the stakeholders.

Event organisers can set up a special event routing for the Nunav app. They define parking spaces, that can be opened and closed in real time. During the event, the number of vehicles being routed to the parking space is displayed. For different visitor roles and touring coaches, individual parking spaces can be defined. If for one role several parking spaces are available, the visitor is routed to the fastest reachable one. This allows intelligent routing to park and ride facilities outside the city centre from where the visitors will reach the event with public transport.

Local authorities define corridors for the event routing. They can monitor the traffic state on the road network provided by FCD from various sources and set up virtual road closures to influence traffic. When actual roadblocks are set up, they are entered via the dashboard too and effect the routing of visitors and residents immediately. Prior to the event, strategic traffic management scenarios can be defined and then activated on demand when needed.

Integrated public transport: Park and ride facilities are located outside the city centre and provide good access to public transport. They can be added as parking spaces for an event reducing the entry barrier for public transport significantly. Events where inner-city parking space is rare or simply not available, routing to the next free park and ride parking lot is a good compromise to make the event happen in the first place and make the change of transport mode to public transport more attractive.

NUNAV Navigation App and Collaborative Routing

Visitors wanting to follow the recommended routes to a special event only need to install the NUNAV Navigation App on their smartphone which is available free of charge in the app stores for iPhone and Android. The app connects vehicles with each other and with the local traffic management authorities.

Connected: The NUNAV Navigation App is connected to the internet where the routing is performed in the cloud. From there it receives TIC information and other sources on road closures. Additionally, traffic management instructions e.g. actual or virtual road closures and mandatory corridors can be distributed in real time by the respective authorities.

Collaborative: All vehicles using the NUNAV Navigation App share their routing strategy with each other and constitute a cooperative swarm. A redundantly distributed cloud service calculates a route for an individual vehicle and is aware of the assigned routes for all other vehicles using the NUNAV App and predicts their impact on the travel time for each road segment over the entire trip duration. With collaborative routing, traffic flow is distributed on the road network based on road capacities and respective speed limits before congestion occurs. With a sufficient market share, congestions can even be prevented.

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Automated: Traffic predictions are made from FCD and are taken into account in real time for the calculation of the fastest route. The optimal route is quasi-continuously recalculated for each vehicle. Therefore, congested roads are automatically avoided without manual intervention.

Multi-vehicle routing: The (re-)calculation of a 50 km long route is performed in less than half a second by a distributed cloud server infrastructure. The multi-vehicle routing scales to thousands of vehicles as the server instances communicate via a reservation service which distributes the knowledge about the requested road usage [4].

Parking: Visitors can select the event by simply typing in the event's name and are routed towards a free parking space. Not visible to them, are the various available parking lots in vicinity to the event location. The parking space reachable with lowest traffic impact is automatically chosen. The route to these dynamic destinations is managed through corridors defined by the authorities, the final destination is defined by the parking managers and their local staff or under certain preconditions can be taken back by the traffic management agency if the situation adheres to it.

Visitor role: Users identify their role by selecting a special role, e.g. "press" or "visitor with disabilities" and are then routed to their designated parking space or array of parking spaces. Touring coach drivers can be provided special routes to their final destination taking into account the strategic traffic management corridors and road closures for heavy vehicles.

Case study 1 - Agritechnica 2017/2019 [5]

During the world's leading fair of agricultural machinery Agritechnica 2017, the traffic management authority of Lower Saxony/Region Hanover implemented for the first time ever their strategic traffic management in the collaborative navigation apps NUNAV Navigation and NUNAV Bus. Basically, only major roads were virtually made available to cars. For buses the most direct way "Messeschnellweg" was made virtually unavailable. A crossing bridge had and still has a weight restriction for vehicles with 7.5 t, but the local deviation can only handle individual buses, but not 3 or more buses arriving at the same time. The risk of vehicle drivers who block one of the main inner-city access gateways because they enter a junction and get stuck in the middle of it, was simply too high.

During peak time up to 800 buses arrived. Out of these, 55% had a license plate from Russia, Sweden, Finland. Within the remaining buses, NUNAV Bus had a market share of 35%, freeing up 8 km road length on "Messeschnellweg".

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Figure - Routing restrictions defined by event organisers and local authorities. Routing corridors to the fair ground are depicted in blue. Within the red bounding box, visitors are routed on the corridors when using the event navigation. The virtual road blockage for buses is marked with a no entry sign.

Figure - Map of event traffic at the Helene Fischer concert in Hannover on Tuesday July 17, 2018. The traces of actual vehicles using the event navigation feature in NUNAV are shown in blue. The triangles mark traffic jams occurring at 18:00. They were expected by the road authorities and they set up virtual road closures for NUNAV drivers shown in red, to preemptively prevent them entering streets before they get congested. The parking icons denote the parking space close to the location and an alternative parking space.

Case study 2 - Helene Fischer 2018 [6]

The inner city HDI-arena is home of the major league team “Hannover 96”. At several occasions per year, concerts take place in the HDI-arena. Naturally, concerts have a completely different spectator group than the local soccer team, because they are mostly comprised of people coming further way as opposed to soccer fans from the Hanover Region. The event took place during the week and collided with the usual rush-hour with people commuting from work to home and therefore leaving the city. The prognosis for the inner-city traffic status was classified as highly difficult, especially since the main local parking space “Schützenplatz”, could only be operated at 40% of its usual capacity. Compensation parking areas at a reasonable walking distance of 20 minutes were partly available, but way outside the usual access routes and digital signage was not an option for the following reasons: (1) the large number of signs needed, (2) its inability to react to traffic situations, (3) its inability to deviate in case of a blocked inter junction and (4) budgetary restraints of the involved parties. The traffic management agency Lower Saxony/Region Hanover set up several virtual corridors within the NUNAV navigation apps. From a strategic point of view, the main access routes were not included in the corridors available for NUNAV users. The twofold strategy also incorporated stationary digital signage used in every soccer match to direct visitors and the same number of security personnel and police officers were present, as it was the first time this strategy was put into place.

From 4000 official car parking visitors, an impressive 11% reached the officially designated parking areas. None of them went to the main parking “Schützenplatz”, largely avoiding the local traffic jams. In the aftermaths of the event, the historic probe data was video-recorded and made available to the authorities. The evaluation of the recording showed that 98% of all NUNAV users followed the navigation turn-by-turn instructions guiding them along the predefined virtual corridors to the designated parking area. The actual travel times agreed well with the predictions with a mean error of 2 %.

Case study 3 HAJ Hannover Marathon [7]

In 2020, the 30th Hanover marathon takes place. Work with the local marathon event organizers started in 2018, during which the marathon course was digitized and made available to all NUNAV users by bringing turn-by-turn instructions. Typically, people living within a marathon course, are informed by mail where the course is heading and where they could cross the course. By digitising the course, smartphone users simply state their destination and receive a route to it. Either avoiding the course altogether or directing them directly towards one of the crossing points according to the time of travel.

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Figure - Map of the road closures during the 2019 Hannover Marathon. It was handed out to residents [8]. Crossing points for vehicles are marked with car symbols.

Figure - Park and ride facilities used during the Pink concert. The event location is depicted as purple circle. Depending on the origin of the visitors, they were routed to the fastest reachable parking space.

Case study 4 - Pink 2019 [9]

Just as in 2018, several concerts took place in 2019. Some of them during a time were virtually no local parking areas were available within a reasonable walking distance of 20 minutes to the HDI-arena. Most of the concerts were mid-week events, each time colliding with the local rush hour.

The traffic management agency Lower Saxony/Region Hanover identified several park and ride parking areas within the Region of Hanover. These park and ride facilities were set up as the users' destination in NUNAV. At the same time, users were informed through various channels, that NUNAV would direct them to a park and ride parking area, from where concert goers could take the free public transport to their final destination within 10 to 20 minutes travel time. Via information screen users got informed about the official travel recommendation. This adds a new dimension to traditional traffic management as it not only explains traffic management aspects, but it positions itself as an integral part of peoples travel arrangements. In this context, the digitalization process of traffic management requires traffic management operators to work closely with communication and marketing specialists to get the customer journey right. This breaks with the tradition of traffic being talked about or broadcasted and delivers traveller information with turn-by-turn instructions right into the palm of user's hands on their smartphone.

From a cities perspective this adds to its attractiveness, as now vehicles can be parked on the city outskirts lowering congestion and avoiding CO₂ emissions by shortening the distance travelled by car and keeping cars away from inner cities. In our findings, this amounts to about 3 t of CO₂ per event per 1000 concert goers.

Conclusion

Over the course of two years several large-scale events have been accompanied ranging from concerts to trade fairs on the world largest exhibition ground. With a market share of around 10% for NUNAV among visitors arriving by car, the traffic jams expected by the road authorities could be avoided. Directing visitors directly to a free parking space lead to a positive user experience. By providing a mobile navigation app where users share their travel intend e.g. driving to a special event, traffic management authorities can distinguish between event visitors and regular traffic and give customised advice. This introduces a new level of granularity to traffic management. As the routing in the navigation app follows traffic management instructions, traffic becomes manageable again in the smart phone era. Sending traffic directly to a free parking lot during large scale mass events reduces park search traffic affecting feeder streets and frees up road capacity for vehicles following their unconnected navigation systems suggestions. One risk of virtual road closures and corridors is users switching to a competing navigation app, that does not follow the traffic management instructions. To prevent this, the benefits for users have to be communicated clearly but also the virtual restrictions cannot be too restrictive. Urban traffic can be improved further by incorporating park and ride facilities in combination with public transport. On average the equivalent of 22-32 km car usage per vehicle can be saved by simply not travelling to the final destination by car. In a further study, the effects on an entire city level have to be investigated. As these cars make room, average speeds on inner-city streets are increasing. This improves both the quality

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of life of residents and the user experience of concert goers, as they spend less time on congested roads and start the event at the park and ride facility.

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